

Functional Javascript and Quantum Circuit Equivalence

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Abstract

[한국어] 함수형 프로그래밍과 양자 컴퓨터의 회로 구성은 호환 가능한 구조를 이룬다. 이에 대한 실증적 증거로 Javascript의 표준 버전인 ECMAScript를 예로 들 수 있다.

[English] Functional programming is equivalent to making circuits in quantum computing, consisting compatible mapping each other. For the real-world proof of its implementation, ECMAScript which is standardization of Javascript can be an example.

1 Introduction

In this paper, with well-known programming language Javascript, compatibility between Javascript and building quantum computing circuits will be discussed.

2 JSFuck: Javascript with Only Brackets

2.1 Function Consists of Sets

JSFuck is esoteric programming language method using javascript written by Martin Kleppe at 2012[[JSF\(\)](#)]. JSFuck uses only six characters while writing code: [,], (,), !, and +[[Wikipedia\(2024\)](#)]. As following basic example, any functional property can be driven from notation of set:

- false \Rightarrow ![]
- true \Rightarrow !![]
- undefined \Rightarrow [[][]]
- NaN \Rightarrow +[![]]
- 0 \Rightarrow +[]
- 1 \Rightarrow +!+[]
- 2 \Rightarrow !+[]+!+[]
- 10 \Rightarrow [+!+[]]+[+[]]
- Array \Rightarrow []
- Number \Rightarrow +[]
- String \Rightarrow []+[]
- Boolean \Rightarrow ![]
- Function \Rightarrow []["filter"]
- eval \Rightarrow []["filter"]["constructor"](CODE)()
- window \Rightarrow []["filter"]["constructor"]("return this")()

And so on. These cases demonstrate the well-defined precondition in Turing-complete programming language that can only use set (array) notation to configure function and only resort to last state in execution without giving any further additional command. This esoteric method is possible under pure Javascript no more than ECMA standard ECMAScript[[ECM\(\)](#)].

2.2 Implications of JSFuck

There are two aspects of JSFuck that imply possible appliance to quantum computer circuits. Under well-defined Turing-complete programming language:

1. Only with variants to set up function is possible.
2. Any stateless function can be finite set of command set.

which are main constituents in quantum computing, first is a qubit and the other is to measure.

3 Quantum Circuit-ECMAScript Equivalences

1. Qubit-State Equivalence
2. Quantum Gates-Function Equivalence
3. Measurement-Execution Equivalence
4. Asynchronous Equivalence

4 Implementation: Reactive Quantum Programming

Reactive programming is of observer pattern[Gamma et al.(1995)Gamma, Helm, Johnson, and Vlissides]. With regarding quantum circuits being fully functional method in their operation in code, any quantum circuit can be implemented as reactive pattern.

```
1 function CircuitFeeder(Qubits) {
2   return new Promise((resolve, reject) => {
3     setTimeout(async () => {
4       const success = await QuantumCircuit(Qubits);
5       if (success) {
6         resolve(success);
7       } else {
8         throw new Error('Quantum Circuit Failure');
9       }
10    }, 1000);
11  });
12 }
13
14 const subject = new Subject();
15 const observer1 = new Observer('Bloch Sphere');
16 const observer2 = new Observer('Probability Distribution');
17
18 subject.subscribe(observer1);
19 subject.subscribe(observer2);
20
21 let qubits = [...]; // Initial qubit objects to go through quantum circuit gate
22
23 CircuitFeeder(qubits)
24   .then(r1 => {
25     console.log('Promise resolved:', r1);
26     CircuitFeeder(r1)
27       .then(r2 => {
28         console.log('Promise resolved:', r2);
29         subject.notify(r2);
30       })
31       .catch(error => {
32         console.error('Promise rejected:', error);
33         subject.notify(error);
34       });
35   })
36   .catch(error => {
37     console.error('Promise rejected:', error);
38     subject.notify(error);
39   });
```

Listing 1: Implementation Example

5 Conclusion

In conclusion, any functional programming based on Javascript(JavaScript) code is convertible with quantum circuit in a pragmatic context. And with its implementation in observer design pattern, quantum circuit can be practically assembled naturally with classical codes.

References

- [ECM()] ECMAScript® 2025 Language Specification — tc39.es. tc39.es/ecma262/. [Accessed 13-07-2024].
- [JSF()] JSFuck - Write any JavaScript with 6 Characters: [](!)+ — jsfuck.com. <https://jsfuck.com/>. [Accessed 12-07-2024].
- [Gamma et al.(1995)Gamma, Helm, Johnson, and Vlissides] Erich Gamma, Richard Helm, Ralph Johnson, and John Vlissides. *Design patterns: elements of reusable object-oriented software*. Pearson Deutschland GmbH, 1995.
- [Wikipedia(2024)] Wikipedia. JSFuck — Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia. <http://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=JSFuck&oldid=1231030778>, 2024. [Online; accessed 13-July-2024].